

SSH Narrative CV Template

Template introduction:

The purpose of this template is to **facilitate structured and evidence-based input of narrative information to support assessment**. Building on the **Résumé for Researchers template**, from the Royal Society, was first enhanced by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV) in the context of the GraspOS project, to incorporate a **broad range of qualities, impacts, contributions and Open Science practices**. Within the GraspOS pilot on Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), led by OPERAS, other elements were included to address **SSH nuances** and make space to better describe SSH common outputs and research activities.

Modules

Personal details

ORCID: _____

Add a **short bio** including your education details, key qualifications and relevant positions you have held.

Suggested length: up to 400 words.

Maximum length: 600 words

Personal statement

Provide a personal statement that reflects on your overarching goals and motivation for the activities in which you have been involved.

Suggested length: up to 200 words.

Maximum length : 300 words

Module 1 – How have you contributed to the generation of knowledge?

This module allows you to explain how you have contributed to the generation of new ideas and hypotheses and which key skills you have used to develop them, including the methodological approach to produce knowledge. You can present a selection of outputs, with a description of why they are of particular relevance and why they are considered in the context of knowledge generation. Relevant outputs can include data sets and related-data papers, academic or non-academic books, scientific and non-scientific articles, conference publications, other types of publications, translation work, educational products, policy briefs, non-traditional outputs (artwork, exhibitions, performances, 3D models...) and any others that you consider important. Prioritise the outputs in Open Access. It can also be used to highlight how you have communicated on your ideas and research results, both written and verbally, the funding and any awards that you have received.

Tips (i)

- Use the [CRediT Contributor Roles](#) taxonomy to articulate your contributions to papers and collaborative projects.
- For a team project, mention your specific contributions.
- Remember to focus on quality over quantity.
- Demonstrate your commitment to open and transparent research practices, including how you manage and share data, methods, and findings, and how you follow FAIR principles.
- Consider providing information on work that is not only in open access, but also a contribution to the development of Open Science more broadly (i.e. open source software for sustaining a service, an infrastructure, or code for doing analysis of data)

Suggested length: up to 400 words.

Maximum length: 600 words

List your Open Science Outputs

ADD DOI

ADD DOI

ADD DOI

Module 2 – How have you contributed to the development of teams or individuals?

This module allows you to highlight your critical expertise provided to the success of a team or individual team members, encompassing project management and implementation. This might involve participating in or leading specific tasks or work packages, or writing and revising reports. Additionally, you can detail your teaching activities, involvement in training, workshops, or summer schools, and the supervision of students and colleagues. You can mention any mentoring of members in your field and the support you've provided for the advancement of colleagues, including peer-to-peer support. Furthermore, this module lets you describe instances where you exerted strategic leadership, such as establishing collaborations, or how you shaped the direction of a team, organisation, company, or institution. Finally, describe how you have supported or influenced the adoption of Open Science practices. This could include encouraging early sharing of results (such as pre-registration), helping others implement open methods or data sharing in project planning, or fostering collaborative practices. The emphasis should be on how your actions have helped others engage with Open Science.

Tips

- Instead of just listing the number of people you have supervised or mentored, consider describing how you supported their development and the impact of your guidance.
- Highlight any challenges you faced in collaborations or partnerships and how you contributed to their success.
- Explain how you have contributed to inclusivity while managing or mentoring.
- Guidance for Early Career Researchers: even if you did not lead, describe how you contributed to important work: e.g., in a project, you can detail your tasks, or how you added your inputs to a new proposal. Consider other forms of providing peer-to-peer support (e.g., giving feedback to an article draft, or slides for a Conference...)

Suggested length: up to 400 words.

Maximum length: 600 words

Module 3 – How have you contributed to the wider research community?

This module can describe various activities you have engaged in and how they support the wider research community. It can be used to mention activities such as editing, reviewing, translating and other practices that value multilingualism, refereeing, committee work and your contributions to the evaluation of researchers and research projects. You can also detail your involvement in the organisation of conferences or similar events targeting the research community. It can highlight contributions to increasing research integrity and improving research culture (gender equality, diversity, mobility of researchers, reward and recognition of researchers' various activities). You can also emphasise activities that can strengthen inter/trans/multi disciplinary collaborations. It can be used to mention appointments to positions of responsibility such as committee membership and corporate roles within your department, institution or organisation, and recognition by invitation within your sector.

Suggested length: up to 400 words.

Maximum length: 600 words

Tips

- Highlight Open Peer Review practices, if applicable.
- Detail what you have achieved on a committee or in a position of responsibility.
- As a leader, describe how you encouraged the uptake of open science practices within your team or organisation through incentivisation or recognition of specific practices (e.g. new policies, activities, training & awareness events)
- Guidance for Early Career Researchers: consider how your work connects to other departments in your university or disciplinary communities beyond your immediate team. You may be working in smaller settings, but your contributions still matter (sharing resources or tools, contributing to joint outputs, engaging in interdisciplinary work, or helping organise academic activities).

Module 4 – How have you contributed to broader society?

This module can include examples of societal engagement, knowledge exchange, and their potential societal impact. It can include engagement with diverse stakeholders such as media (e.g. interviews for newspapers, websites, TV or radio programmes), industry, or third sector (e.g. charities). You can highlight diverse activities to the wider public, such as events (exhibitions, Science days, European Researchers Night) to raise awareness about your research. It can describe how other channels, such as blogs, social media, webinars are used to engage with different audiences. You can explain how you engaged in citizen science initiatives and participatory projects, including non-professional researchers throughout the scientific process. It can be used to highlight efforts to advise policy-makers at local, national or international level.

Suggested length: up to 400 words.

Maximum length: 600 words

Tips

- Raising awareness about your research can offer diverse benefits. Describe any potential impact on social **change**, stimulating **economic development**, contributing to **environmental sustainability**, enhancing **public health**, or enriching **cultural understanding**. Reflect on how engaging with diverse stakeholders can transform your findings into tangible societal impact.
- Describe how the involvement of citizens could benefit your research approach and create positive effects for society.
- Guidance for Early Career Researchers: describe how your research interests could have a potential long term impact on society. While demonstrating immediate impact may not be possible, you could highlight the relevance of your topic to certain key economic, environmental, health or cultural issues.

Additions

Mention career breaks, secondments, volunteering, part-time work and **other relevant experience (including time spent in different sectors)** that might have affected your progression as a researcher.

Please note that you are not required to provide this information. If you choose to provide additional information, this will be seen by the panel and reviewers even if it references a sensitive issue. We encourage you to focus on how the issue has affected your career, rather than expanding on the issue itself. Do not use this section to describe additional skills, experiences or outputs, as this information will not be assessed.

Suggested length: up to 200 words.

Maximum length : 300 words